

Certain q-Kober fractional integral operator of generalized basic hypergeometric functions and q-polynomials

Jayprakash Yadav

Prahladrai Dalmia Lioms College of Commerce and Economics
Mumbai 401107

Abstract

The object of this paper is to established the Kober fractional integral operator of the generalized basic hypergeometric function. Interestingly Kober fractional integral operator of various q-polynomials have been expressed in terms of the basic analogue of Kampè de Fèriet function. Some special cases have been deduced as an application of main result.

Keywords:

Generalized basic hypergeometric functions, Kober fractional integral operator, Kampè de Fèriet function.

MSC2020 **Mathematical Sciences Classification:** Primary 33D15, Secondary 26A33.

1 Introduction

For $q < 1$ and real or compleex a , the q -shifted factorial is defined as

$$(a, q)_n = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } n = 0; \\ (1 - a)(1 - aq)(1 - aq^2) \dots (1 - aq^{n-1}) & \text{if } n \in N. \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

The q-gamma function is given as

$$\Gamma_q(z) = \frac{(q; q)_\infty}{(q^z; q)_\infty} (1 - q)^{1-z}. \quad (1.2)$$

In terms of gamma the equation (1) can be expressed as

$$(a; q)_n = \frac{\Gamma_q(a+n)}{\Gamma_q(a)}(1-q)^n. \tag{1.3}$$

Also

$$(x-y)_\nu = x^\nu \left(\frac{y}{x}; q\right)_\nu \tag{1.4}$$

The generalised basic hypergeometric Serie [2, (1.2.22), p.4] is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} & {}_r\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s \end{matrix}; q, z \right] \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1; q)_n (a_2; q)_n \dots (a_r; q)_n}{(q; q)_n (b_1; q)_n (b_2; q)_n \dots (b_s; q)_n} \left[(-1)^n q^{\binom{n}{2}} \right]^{1+s-r} z^n. \end{aligned} \tag{1.5}$$

The Basic analogue of Kober fractional integral operator (cf. Agarwal [1]) is given by

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \{f(x)\} = \frac{x^{-\eta-\alpha}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-tq)_{\alpha-1} t^\eta f(t) d_q t. \tag{1.6}$$

where $\Re(\alpha) > 0, |q| < 1$ and $\eta \in R$

Also the basic integral (cf. Gasper & Rahman [3]) is given by

$$\int_0^x f(x) d_q t = x(1-q) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k f(zq^k). \tag{1.7}$$

In view of (1.7) the equation (1.6) can be written as

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \{f(x)\} = \frac{-q^{-\alpha} x^{1-\eta} z^{\eta-1} (1-q) \left(\frac{zq}{x}; q\right)_\alpha}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{\left(\frac{z}{x} q^{1+\alpha}; q\right)_r q^{\eta r}}{\left(\frac{zq}{x}; q\right)_r (1 - \frac{x}{z} q^{-(n+r)})} f(zq^r). \tag{1.8}$$

which on replacing x by z we have

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \{f(z)\} = \frac{-q^{-\alpha} (1-q) (q; q)_\alpha}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(q^{1+\alpha}; q)_r q^{\eta r}}{(q; q)_r (1 - q^{-(n+r)})} f(zq^r). \tag{1.9}$$

Heine’s q-analogue of Gauss summation formula is given by

$${}_2\phi_1(a, b; c; q, c/ab) = \frac{(c/a, c/b; q)_\infty}{(c, c/ab; q)_\infty}. \tag{1.10}$$

the above formula is valid for $|c/ab| < 1$. For the terminating case when $a = q^{-n}$, (1.10) reduces to

$${}_2\phi_1(q^{-n}, b; c; q, cq^n/b) = \frac{(c/b; q)_\infty}{(c; q)_\infty}. \tag{1.11}$$

By changing the order of summation it follows from (1.11) that

$${}_2\phi_1(q^{-n}, b; c; q, q) = \frac{(c/b; q)_\infty}{(c; q)_\infty} b^n. \tag{1.12}$$

The q-binomial theorem due to Cauchy [1843], Heine[1847] is given by

$${}_1\phi_0(a; -; q, z) = \frac{(az; q)_\infty}{(z; q)_\infty} \quad |z| < 1, |q| < 1. \tag{1.13}$$

The basic analogue of Kampè de Fèriet function (cf. Srivastava and Karlson[3]) is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} & \phi_{C;D;D'}^{A;B;B'} \left[\begin{matrix} (a) : (b); (b') \\ (c) : (d); (d') \end{matrix} ; q, x, y \right] \\ &= \sum_{m,n \geq 0} \frac{\prod_{p=1}^A (a_p; q)_{m+n} \prod_{p=1}^B (b_p; q)_m \prod_{p=1}^{B'} (b'_p; q)_n}{\prod_{p=1}^C (c_p; q)_{m+n} \prod_{p=1}^D (d_p; q)_m \prod_{p=1}^{D'} (d'_p; q)_n} \frac{x^m y^n}{(q; q)_m (q; q)_n} \end{aligned} \tag{1.14}$$

where $|x| < 1, |y| < 1$ and $0 < |q| < 1$.

The abnormal type of generalized basic hypergeometric Serie is defined as

$${}_r\phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; q, z \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s; q^\lambda \end{matrix} \right] = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; q)_n}{(q, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s; q)_n} z^n q^{\lambda n(n-1)/2}. \tag{1.15}$$

where $\lambda \geq 0$.

In the proof of the main result, I will use the following definition of various q-polynomials in the proof of the main results: The q-Laguerre polynomials

$$L_n^{(\alpha)}(x; q) = \frac{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_n}{(q; q)_n} {}_1\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n} \\ q^{\alpha+1} \end{matrix} ; q, -xq^n \right] \tag{1.16}$$

The Wall polynomials (or Little q-Laguerre polynomial)

$$W_n(x; b, q) = (-1)^n (b; q)_n q^{n(n+1)/2} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, 0 \\ b \end{matrix} ; q, x \right] \tag{1.17}$$

$$\Gamma_n^{\alpha,\beta}(z; q) = \frac{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_n}{(q; q)_n} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^{\alpha+\beta+n+1} \\ q^{\alpha+1} \end{matrix} ; q, -xq \right] \quad (1.18)$$

The Stieltjes-Wigert polynomials

$$S_n(x; q) = {}_1\phi_0 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n} \\ - \end{matrix} ; q^1, -x \right] \quad (1.19)$$

The q-Hahn polynomials

$$Q_n(x; \alpha, \beta, \nu; q) = {}_3\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, \alpha\beta q^{n+1}, x \\ \alpha q, \nu q \end{matrix} ; q, q \right] \quad (1.20)$$

The q-Meixner polynomials

$$M_n(x; \beta, \gamma; q) = (\beta; q)_n {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, x \\ \beta \end{matrix} ; q, \frac{q^{n+1}}{\gamma} \right] \quad (1.21)$$

The q-Charlier polynomials

$$C_n(x; \alpha; q) = {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, x \\ 0 \end{matrix} ; q, -\frac{q^{n+1}}{\alpha} \right] \quad (1.22)$$

The q-Krawtchouk polynomials

$$K_n(x; a, N; q) = {}_3\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, -a^{-1}q^n, x \\ q^{-N}, 0 \end{matrix} ; q, q \right] \quad (1.23)$$

The q-Konhauser polynomials of first Kind

$$Z_n^{\{\alpha\}}(z; k; q) = \frac{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_{nk}}{(q^k; q^k)_n} \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(q^{-nk}; q^k)_i}{(q^k; q^k)_i} \frac{q^{(1/2)ki(k-1)+ki(n+\alpha+1)}}{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_{ik}} x^{ik} \quad (1.24)$$

The q-Konhauser polynomials of second Kind

$$Y_n^{\{\alpha\}}(z; k; q) = \frac{1}{(q; q)_n} \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{q^{r(r-1)/2} x^r}{(q; q)_r} \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(q^{-r}; q)_i (q^{1+\alpha+i}; q^k)_n q^i}{(q; q)_i} \quad (1.25)$$

The bibasic form of the q-analogue of the Bedient polynomials of first kind is given by:

$$R_n(\alpha, \beta; q, x) = \frac{(\alpha; q)_n (2x/\sqrt{\alpha})^n}{(q; q)_n} {}_3\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^{-n+1}; \beta/\alpha \\ - \end{matrix} ; q^2, q, (q/x)^n \right] \quad (1.26)$$

The bibasic form of the q-analogue of the Bedient polynomials of second kind is given by:

$$G_n(\alpha, \beta; q, x) = \frac{(\alpha; q)_n (2x)^n}{(q; q)_n (\alpha\beta; q)_n} {}_3\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^{-n+1}; q^{1-n}/\alpha\beta \\ - \end{matrix} ; q^2, q, (1/x)^n \right] \quad (1.27)$$

and the Gegenbaur polynomials

$$R_n(\alpha, \beta; q, x) = \frac{(\alpha; q)_n (2x/\sqrt{\alpha})^n}{(q; q)_n} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^{-n+1}; - \\ - \end{matrix} ; q^2, q, (q/\alpha x)^n \right] \quad (1.28)$$

The generalized multibasic hypergeometric function is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \phi \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; c_{11}, c_{12}, \dots, c_{1r_1}; \dots; c_{m1}, c_{m2}, \dots, c_{mr_m} \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s; d_{11}, d_{12}, \dots, d_{1s_1}; \dots; d_{m1}, d_{m2}, \dots, d_{ms_m} \end{matrix} ; q, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m; z \right] \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r; q)_n}{(q, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s; q)_n} z^n \prod_{j=1}^m \frac{(c_{j1}, c_{j2}, \dots, c_{jr_j}; q_j)_n}{(d_{j1}, d_{j2}, \dots, d_{js_j}; q_j)_n}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.29)$$

where $0 < |q_j|, |q| < 1, |z| < 1$.

2 Main Results

$$I_q^{\alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)})_r \phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} ; q, z \right] \right\}$$

$$= \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1-q)(q; q)_{\alpha}(q^{1+\eta+\alpha}; q)_{\infty}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^{\eta}; q)_{\infty}} {}_{r+1}\phi_{s+1} \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r, q^{\eta} \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s, q^{1+\eta+\alpha} \end{matrix}; q, z \right] \quad (2.1)$$

$$I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ \frac{(1-q^{-(n+r)})(q^{1+\eta}; q)_r}{(q^{2(1+\eta)+\alpha}; q)_r} \right\} = \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1-q)(q; q)_{\alpha}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \Pi \left[\begin{matrix} q^{1+2\eta}, q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q \\ q^{2(1+\eta)+\alpha}, q^{\eta} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (2.2)$$

$$I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ \frac{(1-q^{-(n+r)})(q^{-r}; q)_r q^{n(1-\eta)}}{(q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_r} \right\} = \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1-q)(q; q)_{\alpha}(q^{\eta}; q)_r}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_r} q^{r(1+\alpha)} \quad (2.3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1-q^{-(r+\alpha)})Q_n(z; \alpha, \beta, \nu; q) \right\} \\ &= \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_{\alpha}}{q^{\alpha}\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \phi_{0:1;2}^{1:1;2} \left[\begin{matrix} z : q^{1+\alpha}; q^{-n}, \alpha\beta q^{n+1} \\ - : z \quad ; \alpha q, \nu q \end{matrix} ; q, q^{\eta}, q \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1-q^{-(r+\alpha)})M_n(z; \beta, \gamma; q) \right\} \\ &= \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_{\alpha}(\beta; q)_n}{q^{\alpha}\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \phi_{0:1;1}^{1:1;1} \left[\begin{matrix} z : q^{1+\alpha}; q^{-n} \\ - : z \quad ; \beta \end{matrix} ; q, q^{\eta}, \frac{q^{n+1}}{\gamma} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1-q^{-(r+\alpha)})C_n(z; \alpha; q) \right\} \\ &= \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_{\alpha}}{q^{\alpha}\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \phi_{0:1;0}^{1:1;1} \left[\begin{matrix} z : q^{1+\alpha}; q^{-n} \\ - : z \quad ; - \end{matrix} ; q, q^{\eta}, -\frac{q^{n+1}}{\alpha} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1-q^{-(r+\alpha)})K_n(z; a, N; q) \right\} \\ &= \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_{\alpha}}{q^{\alpha}\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \phi_{0:1;2}^{1:1;2} \left[\begin{matrix} z : q^{1+\alpha}; q^{-n}, -a^{-1}q^n \\ - : z \quad ; q^{-N}, 0 \end{matrix} ; q, q^{\eta}, q \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

$$I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1-q^{-j-\alpha})Z_n^{\{\alpha\}}(z; k; q) \right\}$$

$$= \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty (q^{\alpha+1}; q)_{nk}}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty (q^k; q^k)_n} \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(q^{-nk}; q^k)_i (q^\eta; q)_{ik}}{(q^k; q^k)_i (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_{ik}} \frac{q^{(1/2)ki(k-1)+ki(n+\alpha+1)}}{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_{ik}} z^{ik} \tag{2.8}$$

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-j-\alpha}) Y_n^{\{\alpha\}}(z; k; q) \right\} \\ = \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty (q; q)_n} \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(q^\eta; q)_r q^{r(r-1)/2} x^r}{(q; q)_r (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_r} \sum_{i=0}^r \frac{(q^{-r}; q)_i (q^{1+\alpha+i}; q^k)_n q^i}{(q; q)_i} \tag{2.9}$$

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-j-\alpha}) R_n(\alpha, \beta; q, x) \right\} = \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty (\alpha; q)_n (2z/\sqrt{\alpha})^n}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty (q; q)_n} \\ \times {}_4\phi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^{-n+1}; \beta/\alpha, & q^{-\alpha-\eta} \\ & ; q^2, q, \frac{q^{n+\alpha+1}}{x^n} \\ - & : \beta, q^{1-n}/\alpha, q^{1-\eta} \end{matrix} \right] \tag{2.10}$$

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-j-\alpha}) G_n(\alpha, \beta; q, x) \right\} = \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty (\alpha; q)_n (2z)^n}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty (q; q)_n (\alpha\beta; q)_n} \\ \times {}_4\phi_3 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^{-n+1}; q^{1-n}/\alpha\beta, & q^{-\alpha-\eta} \\ & ; q^2, q, \frac{q^{\alpha+1}}{x^n} \\ - & : q^{1-n}/\alpha, q^{1-n}/\beta, q^{1-\eta} \end{matrix} \right] \tag{2.11}$$

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-j-\alpha}) C_n^{\{\alpha\}}(z; q) \right\} = \frac{-(1-q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty (\alpha; q)_n (2z/\sqrt{\alpha})^n}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty (q; q)_n} \\ \times {}_3\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^{-n+1}; & q^{-\alpha-\eta} \\ & ; q^2, q, \frac{q^{n+\alpha+1}}{\alpha x^n} \\ - & : q^{1-n}/\alpha, q^{1-\eta} \end{matrix} \right] \tag{2.12}$$

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)}) \phi \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r; c_{11}, \dots, c_{1r_1}; \dots; c_{m1}, \dots, c_{mr_m} \\ & ; q, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m; z \\ b_1, \dots, b_s; d_{11}, \dots, d_{1s_1}; \dots; d_{m1}, \dots, d_{ms_m} \end{matrix} \right] \right\} \\ = \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1-q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\eta+\alpha}; q)_\infty}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty}$$

$$\times \phi \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r, q^\eta: c_{11}, \dots, c_{1r_1}; \dots; c_{m1}, \dots, c_{mr_m} \\ \phantom{a_1, \dots, a_r, q^\eta: c_{11}, \dots, c_{1r_1}; \dots; c_{m1}, \dots, c_{mr_m}}; q, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m; z \\ b_1, \dots, b_s, q^{\alpha+\eta+1}: d_{11}, \dots, d_{1s_1}; \dots; d_{m1}, \dots, d_{ms_m} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (2.13)$$

Proof of the main results:

To prove the result (2.1), take

$$f(z) = (1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)})_r \phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r \\ ; q, z \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} \right]$$

in the equation(1.9). After interchanging the order of summation and using the formula(1.13) and after some simplification , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)})_r \phi_s \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r \\ ; q, z \\ b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s \end{matrix} \right] \right\} \\ &= \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\eta+\alpha}; q)_\infty}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r, q^\eta; q)_r}{(b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s, q^{1+\alpha+\eta})_r} z^r \left[(-1)^r q^{\binom{r}{2}} \right]^{1+s-r} \end{aligned}$$

On making use of equation(1.5), this reduces to result(2.1).

To prove the result (2.2), take

$$f(z) = (1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)}) \frac{(q^{1+\eta}; q)_r}{(q^{2(1+\eta)+\alpha}; q)_r}$$

in the equation (1.9), we obtain

$$I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ \frac{(1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)})(q^{1+\eta}; q)_r}{(q^{2(1+\eta)+\alpha}; q)_r} \right\} = \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} {}_2\phi_1 \left(q^{1+\alpha}, q^{1+\eta}; q^{2(1+\eta)+\alpha}; q, q^\eta \right)$$

Making use of the equation(1.10) this reduces to the result (2.2).

To prove the result (2.3), take

$$f(z) = \frac{(1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)})(q^{-n}; q)_r q^{r(1-\eta)}}{(q^{1+\eta+\alpha}; q)_r}$$

in the equation (1.9), we obtain

$$I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ \frac{(1 - q^{-(n+r)})(q^{-r}; q)_r q^{n(1-\eta)}}{(q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_r} \right\} = \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} {}_2\phi_1 \left(q^{-n}, q^{1+\alpha}; q^{1+\eta+\alpha}; q, q \right)$$

Making use of the equation (1.12) this reduces to the result (2.3).

To prove the result (2.4), take

$$f(z) = \left\{ (1 - q^{-(r+\alpha)})Q_n(z; \alpha, \beta, \nu; q) \right\}$$

in the equation (1.9), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(r+\alpha)})Q_n(z; \alpha, \beta, \nu; q) \right\} \\ &= \frac{-(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_r q^{r\eta}}{(q; q)_r} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(q^{-n}, \alpha\beta q^{n+1}; q)_i (zq^r; q)_i}{(\alpha q, \nu q; q)_i (q; q)_i} q^i \end{aligned}$$

On simplification this can be written as

$$= \frac{-(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(z; q)_{r+i} (q^{\alpha+1}; q)_r (q^{-n}, \alpha\beta q^{n+1}; q)_i}{(z; q)_r (\alpha q, \nu q; q)_i (q; q)_r (q; q)_i} q^{r\eta} q^i$$

In view of equation (1.14), this reduces to the result (2.4).

Proofs of the results (2.5), (2.6) and (2.7) can be seen similarly.

To prove the result (2.8), take

$$f(z) = \left\{ (1 - q^{-j-\alpha})Z_n^{\{\alpha\}}(z; k; q) \right\}$$

in the equation (1.9), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} & I_q^{\eta, \alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-j-\alpha})Z_n^{\{\alpha\}}(z; k; q) \right\} \\ &= \frac{-(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)} \frac{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_{nk}}{(q^k; q^k)_n} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_r q^{r\eta}}{(q; q)_r} \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(q^{-nk}; q^k)_i}{(q^k; q^k)_i} \frac{q^{(1/2)ki(k-1)+ki(n+\alpha+1)}}{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_{ik}} z^{ik} q^{ikr} \end{aligned}$$

Interchanging the order of summation and using the formula(1.13) and after some simplification , we obtain the result the result (2.8).

Result (2.9) can be proved similarly.

To prove the result (2.10), take $f(z) = \{(1 - q^{-j-\alpha})R_n(\alpha, \beta; q, x)\}$ in the equation (1.9). Interchanging the order of summation, we obtain:

$$I_q^{n,\alpha} \{(1 - q^{-j-\alpha})R_n(\alpha, \beta; q, x)\} = \frac{-(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha (\alpha; q)_n (2z/\sqrt{\alpha})^n}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)(q; q)_n} \times$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(q^{-n}, q^{-n+1}; q^2)_i (\beta/\alpha; q)_i (q^n/x^n)^i}{(q; q)_i (\beta, q^{1-n}/\alpha; q)_i} \sum_{r=0}^{\infty} \frac{(q^{\alpha+1}; q)_r q^{r(\eta-i)}}{(q; q)_r}$$

Now using the formula (1.13) and simplifying, we obtain the result (2.10).

The results 2.11 and (2.12) can be proved similarly.

To Prove the result(2.133), take

$$f(z) = (1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)})\phi \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r; c_{11}, \dots, c_{1r_1}; \dots; c_{m1}, \dots, c_{mr_m} \\ ; q, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m; z \\ b_1, \dots, b_s; d_{11}, \dots, d_{1s_1}; \dots; d_{m1}, \dots, d_{ms_m} \end{matrix} \right]$$

in the equation(1.9).Interchanging the order of summation and using the formula (1.133), we obtain the following:

$$I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(\alpha+r)})\phi \left[\begin{matrix} a_1, \dots, a_r; c_{11}, \dots, c_{1r_1}; \dots; c_{m1}, \dots, c_{mr_m} \\ ; q, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_m; z \\ b_1, \dots, b_s; d_{11}, \dots, d_{1s_1}; \dots; d_{m1}, \dots, d_{ms_m} \end{matrix} \right] \right\}$$

$$= \frac{-q^{-\alpha}(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\eta+\alpha}; q)_\infty}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_1, \dots, a_r, q^\eta; q)_n}{(q, b_1, \dots, b_s, q^{\alpha+\eta+1}; q)_n} z^n \prod_{j=1}^m \frac{(c_{j1}, \dots, c_{jr_j}; q_j)_n}{(d_{j1}, \dots, d_{js_j}; q_j)_n}.$$

Now using the definition (1.29), this reduces to the result(2.13).

3 Application of the result (2.1):

In this section, I will evaluate Kober fractional integral operator of some of the basic hypergeometric polynomials as an application of the main result(2.1).The results are listed below.

$$I_q^{n,\alpha} \{(1 - q^{-(r+\alpha)})S_n(z; q)\}$$

$$= \frac{-(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha)(q^\eta; q)_\infty} {}_2\phi_1 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, q^\eta ; q, -z \\ q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q^1 \end{matrix} \right] \tag{3.1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(r+\alpha)}) L_n^{(\alpha)}(z; q) \right\} \\
 &= \frac{-(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{\alpha+1};)_n (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha) (q; q)_n (q^\eta; q)_\infty} {}_2\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, & q^\eta & ; q, -zq^n \\ q^{\alpha+1}, & q^{1+\alpha+\eta} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (3.2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(r+\alpha)}) W_n(z; b; q) \right\} \\
 &= \frac{(-1)^{n+1} (1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha (b; q)_n (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty q^{n(n+1)/2}}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha) (q^\eta; q)_\infty} {}_3\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, & 0 & , & q^\eta \\ & & & ; q, z \\ & b, & q^{1+\alpha+\eta} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (3.33)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & I_q^{n,\alpha} \left\{ (1 - q^{-(r+\alpha)}) \Gamma_n^{\alpha,\beta}(z; q) \right\} \\
 &= \frac{-(1 - q)(q; q)_\alpha (q^{\alpha+l}; q)_n (q^{1+\alpha+\eta}; q)_\infty}{q^\alpha \Gamma_q(\alpha) ((q; q)_n (q^\eta; q)_\infty)} {}_3\phi_2 \left[\begin{matrix} q^{-n}, & q^{\alpha+\beta+n+1}, & q^\eta \\ & & ; q, zq \\ q^{n+1}, & q^{1+\alpha+\eta} \end{matrix} \right] \quad (3.4)
 \end{aligned}$$

Acknowledgement

The author extends the sincere thanks to Dr.S.N.Singh for his unconditional guidance and support which results in the form of this paper.

References

- [1] Agarwal, R.P., Fractional q-derivatives and q-integrals and certain hypergeometric transformations, Ganita 27 (1976), 25-32.
- [2] Gasper, G. and Rahman, M. Basic Hypergeometric Series, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge,1990.
- [3] H. M. Srivastava and P. W. Karlsson, Multiple Gaussian Hypergeometric Series, John Wiley and Sons, Halsted press, New York, 1985.ription
- [4] Slater, L.J., Generalized Hypeergeometric Functions,Cambridge University Press, Cambridge,1966.

- [5] Srivastava, H.M. and Jain, V.K., q-Series Identities and Reducibility of Basic Double Hypergeometric Functions, *Can. J. Math.*, Vol. xxxviii, No. 1, 1986, pp. 215-231.
- [6] Yadav, R.K. and Purohit, S.D., On Applications of q-Fractional Calculus Operators and Transformations Involving Generalized Hypergeometric Basic Functions, *Bull. Pure Appl. Math.*, Vol. 4, No. 1 (2010), 125-132.
- [7] Yadav, Jayprakash and Pandey, N.N., On Certain Transformations of Bivariate Basic Hypergeometric Series using q-Fractional Operators, *South East Asian J. of Math. Math. Sci.* Vol.11, No.1, 2015, pp. 25-30.
- [8] Yadav, Jayprakash, ON TRANSFORMATION OF BASIC HYPERGEOMETRIC FUNCTIONS APPLYING FRACTIONAL q-DIFFERENTIAL OPERATOR, *South East Asian J. of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences*, Vol. 19, No. 3 (2023), pp. 75-80.
- [9] Yadav, Jayprakash and Sahni, Nidhi, On Some Transformations and Summations of Basic Hypergeometric Series-I, *Indian Journal of Natural Sciences*, Vol.14 / Issue 82 / Feb / 2024.